

MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI BOLALAR TISHLARIDA DEMINERALIZATSION JARAYON MAVJUDLIGI VA JADALLIGINI BAHOLASH

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Annotatsiya. Tish kariyesi dunyo bo'ylab eng keng tarqalgan kasalliklardan biridir. U asosan mutant streptokokk kabi kariyesni keltirib chiqaruvchi bakteriyalarning tishlarga yopishib, u yerda shakarlarni parchalab kislotaga hosil qilishi natijasida yuzaga keladi. Erta bolalik kariyesi (EBK) olti yoshgacha bo'lgan bolada biror sut tishida bir yoki undan ortiq (kariyes tufayli) chirigan, tushib ketgan yoki plombalangan tish yuzasining mavjudligi sifatida aniqlanadi. [2,7,10]

Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti (JSST) erta bolalik kariyesini 60 dan 90% gacha tarqalgan global muammo sifatida ko'rsatgan [5]. Yevropa mamlakatlari tomonidan taqdim etilgan statistik ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, 6 yoshdan 12 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalarning 61 foizida kamida bitta kariyes tishi bor va barcha ijtimoiy sinflarda tish kariyesining keng tarqalishi tufayli bu kasallik jamiyatga katta moliyaviy yuk yuklashi mumkin.

Taxminan aholining 35% da davolanmagan tish kariyesi borligi taxmin qilinmoqda. Ftor tish kariyesining oldini olishda asosiy omil bo'lib kelgan bo'lsa-da, aholi orasida qabul qilinishining pasayishi va bolalarda flyuoroz xavfi tufayli samarali muqobillar zarurati mavjud. Gidroksiapatit (GAP; Tarkibida $Ca_5(PO_4)_3(OH)$ bo'lgan tish pastalari ftorsiz alternativalar bo'lib, ular so'nggi paytlarda kariyesga qarshi vositalar sifatida samarali ekanligi isbotlangan.[1,4]

Kalit so'zlar. Karies, demineralizatsiya, remineralizatsiya

ОЦЕНКА НАЛИЧИЯ И ИНТЕНСИВНОСТИ ПРОЦЕССА ДЕМИНЕРАЛИЗАЦИИ ЗУБОВ У ДЕТЕЙ ШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

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Аннотация. Кариес зубов - одно из самых распространенных заболеваний во всем мире. Он в основном возникает в результате того, что кариозные бактерии, такие как мутантный стрептококк, прикрепляются к зубам, разрушая там сахара с образованием кислоты. Кариес раннего детства (КРМ) у детей до шести лет с одним или более молочными зубами (из-за кариеса) определяется как наличие гнилой, выпавшей или пломбированной поверхности зуба. [2,7,10]

Всемирная организация здравоохранения (ВОЗ) обозначила кариес раннего детства как глобальную проблему с распространенностью от 60 до 90%[5]. Согласно статистике, предоставленной европейскими странами, у 61% детей в возрасте от 6 до 12 лет имеется как минимум один кариесный зуб, и из-за широкой распространенности кариеса зубов во всех социальных классах это заболевание может создать значительную финансовую нагрузку на общество.

Предполагается, что примерно у 35% населения имеется нелеченный кариес зубов. Хотя фтор был ключевым фактором в профилактике кариеса зубов, существует необходимость в эффективных альтернативах из-за снижения потребления среди населения и риска флюороза у детей. Гидроксиапатит (ГАП; Зубные пасты, содержащие $\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3(\text{OH})$, являются нефторированными альтернативами, которые в последнее время доказали свою эффективность в качестве противокариозных средств.[1,4]

Ключевые слова. Кариес, деминерализация, реминерализация

ASSESSMENT OF THE PRESENCE AND INTENSITY OF REMINERALIZATION PROCESSES IN THE TEETH OF SCHOOL-AGE CHILDREN

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Abstract. Dental caries is one of the most widespread diseases globally. It primarily occurs when caries-causing bacteria, such as mutant streptococcus, adhere to teeth and break down sugars, producing acid. Early childhood caries (ECC) is defined as the

presence of one or more decayed, missing (due to caries), or filled tooth surfaces in any primary tooth in a child under six years of age. [2,7,10]

The World Health Organization (WHO) has identified early childhood caries as a global problem with a prevalence ranging from 60 to 90%.

The World Health Organization (WHO) has identified early childhood caries as a global problem with a prevalence of 60 to 90%.

According to statistics provided by European countries, 61% of children aged 6 to 12 have at least one caries tooth, and due to the widespread prevalence of dental caries in all social classes, this disease can place a significant financial burden on society.

It is estimated that approximately 35% of the population has untreated dental caries. Although fluorine has been a key factor in the prevention of dental caries, there is a need for effective alternatives due to the decrease in its use among the population and the risk of fluorosis in children. Hydroxyapatite (HAP; Toothpastes containing $\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3(\text{OH})$ are fluorine-free alternatives, which have recently been proven to be effective as anti-cariogenic agents.[1,4]

Keywords. Caries, demineralization, remineralization

Tadqiqot maqsadi. Maktab yoshidagi bolalar tishlarida dog` bosqichidagi kariesni aniqlash ularni davolash samaradorligini oshirishga yordam beradi, chuqur kavakli defektlar hosil bo`lishini va kelajakda kelib chiqadigan suyak va yumshoq to`qimalarda kechadigan asoratlarni oldini oladi.

Materiallar va usullar. Tadqiqotda somatik jihatdan sog`lom sakkizinchi va o`ninchi sinf o`quvchilari (50 kishi: 23 qiz va 27 o`g`il bolalar) ishtirok etdi. Ushbu maktabda faoliyat yuritadigan statsionar stomatologiya kabinetida tekshiruvlar o`tkazildi.

O`tkazilgan tekshiruvlar:

1. KPU indeksi bo'yicha bolalar tishlari holatini aniqlash;
2. Tish kariesining demineralizatsiyasini metilen ko'kning 2% suvli eritmasi bilan bo'yash usuli bilan aniqlash va baholash (Aksamit indeksi);

Natijalar va muhokama. Tadqiqotda ishtirok etgan bolalarning ogʻiz boʻshligʻi kuzatuv davomida quyidagi natijalar qayd etildi:

-Tekshirilgan bolalar KPU indeksi umumiy guruhga nisbatan oʻrtacha 0,53 ni tashkil etdi.

-Qizlar oʻrtasida oʻrtacha KPU indeks koʻrsatgichi 0,49

-Oʻgʻil bolalar oʻrtacha KPU indeksi 0,57

-Metilen ko`kining 2%li eritmasida demineralizatsiyalanayotgan o`choqlarni bo`yash usuli bilan ani`langan Aksamit indeksining o`rtacha ko`rsatgichi o`lchanganlar orasida 2,7 ko`rsatgichni tashkil etdi.

Xulosa. Tadqiqotdan ko`zlangan maqsadga muvofiq maktab yoshidagi bolalar tish yuzasidagi demineralizatsion o`choq hosil qilgan dog` bosqichidagi karieslarning borligi, ularning jadalligi aniqlandi va holatga baho berildi. KPU indeksi natijasiga ko`ra bolalarda tishlarning holati yaxshi ko`rsatgichda deb baholandi. Aksamit indeksi bilan tekshirilgan demineralizatsion jarayonning holati ham qoniqarli. Bu natijalarga asoslangan holda tekshiruvdan o`tkazilgan bolalarga tavsiyalar berildi va remineralizatsiyalovchi "R.O.C.S. Medical Minerals" gelidan foydalanish tavsiyasi berildi

Tavsiyalar:

1. Tish gigiyenasiga e'tibor qaratish bilan bir qatorda remineralizatsiya vositalarini, jumladan ROCS gelini muntazam qo'llash zarur.
2. Profilaktik dasturlarni maktab yoshidagi bolalar uchun keng ko'lamda amalga oshirish tish sog'lig'ini yaxshilashga yordam beradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar.

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